

Barriers to accessing health care services for ethnic minorities in land border areas of Vietnam

Truong Thi Ly ¹ and Vu Van Thu ^{2*}

¹ Faculty of Social work, Trade Union University, Vietnam

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1438-0261>

^{2*} Faculty of Occupational safety and health, Trade Union University, Vietnam

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3134-9670>

Abstract: Vietnam is a country with more than 5,000 km of land border. The majority of the population living in the border areas are ethnic minorities and they live sparsely in villages far apart. In addition to the difficulties in life, ethnic minorities here also face many difficulties in accessing health care services. By using a general approach based on documents, including scientific journal articles, reports, books, and reports published in scientific conference proceedings, legal documents, and statistical reports of Vietnam and the world on public health and health care, the article shows that ethnic minorities living in the land border areas of Vietnam are facing barriers in accessing health care services such as: (1) Geographical and topographical barriers; (2) Economic barriers; (3) Barriers in facilities and human resources for primary health care; (4) Language and cultural barriers; (5) Policy barriers. The actions that Vietnam needs to continue to take to remove barriers, towards the goal of "Health and good life" to promote sustainable development in Vietnam in the current context have also been studied and clarified.

Keywords: ethnic minorities, land borders, health care services, barriers in services.

1. Introduction

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 3 is to ensure healthy lives and promote good health for all at all ages (United Nations, 2015). Improving access to health care services is an important factor in helping them achieve equity in health care access towards achieving the sustainable development goals (European Commission, 2018). However, around the world, ethnic minorities remain a disadvantaged group facing many barriers and difficulties in accessing and enjoying health services and health care compared to the general population (Mental Health Commission, 2016). In most health care systems, ethnic minorities always face barriers in accessing certain services (Ala, 2005). People from ethnic minorities experience inequalities in their access to and experience of health care services (Ajayi, 2021). Ethnic minorities use health care at lower rates, have poorer health outcomes, and have lower life expectancies (Chauhan et al., 2023), (Zhang, Jaswal, & Quint, 2023). Research in the United

Kingdom has shown ethnic inequalities in health care use and quality of care among people with multiple chronic conditions (Hayanga, Stafford, & Bécaries, 2021). In Ireland, ethnic minorities experience a range of psychosocial issues that act as barriers to accessing mental health services and support (Mental Health Commission, 2016). In the United States, disparities exist in both access to and quality of mental health care for racial and ethnic minority groups (Atdjian & Vega, 2005).

Vietnam is one of the countries that has achieved many good results in health care for its people. Although it is a country with relatively low income and limited resources, Vietnam has had remarkable successes in its medical and health care efforts (Gabriele 1, 2006). The Vietnamese government has made many efforts in promulgating and implementing policies to improve access to health care services for ethnic minorities. The State has prioritized allocating investment budgets for primary health care in poor areas, ethnic minority areas and mountainous areas. Ethnic minorities are given free health insurance cards and have their health insurance costs paid by the social insurance agency. Along with that, there are a series of maternal and child health care programs such as implementing the village midwife model and supporting ethnic minority village midwives in difficult areas,... (PT Anh & Viet, 2020). However, besides remarkable achievements, in Vietnam there are still health inequalities (DN Anh & Thao, 2022).

Vietnam is a country with a land border of more than 5,000 km (Vietnam Government, 2022). According to the provisions of the Law on National Borders (Vietnam National Assembly, 2003), Vietnam's land border areas include communes, wards, and towns whose administrative boundaries partly coincide with the national land border. Vietnam shares a border with China to the North, with Laos to the West, and with Cambodia to the Southwest (NA Thu, Phuong, Ha, & Nghiem, 2020). There are currently about 400 communes in the border area nationwide (Vietnam Ethnic Committee & General Statistics Office, 2020). Of which, the land border area is the main residential area of ethnic minorities (Chien, 2024; Muoi, 2021; Thanh, Xuan, & Binh, 2017). The Vietnam - China land border area has up to 26 different ethnic minorities living (Chien, 2024). In the Vietnam - Laos border area, about 80% of the population are ethnic minorities (Thanh et al., 2017). Studies show that the border area is an area that needs a lot of attention from the government (Laksono & Wulandari, 2021), especially in terms of health care services for the people. Communities living in border areas face more challenges in accessing health care services than those living in urban areas (Aina, Sandi, & Johansyah, 2023). People living in border areas have lower chances of using inpatient hospital services than those in other areas (Laksono & Wulandari, 2021). In Vietnam, the rate of access to basic social services including health services for the poor, ethnic minorities and

mountainous areas, especially ethnic minority groups living in border areas, is still very limited (PT Anh & Viet, 2020). Ethnic minorities living in border areas not only face difficulties and deprivation in material and spiritual life but also face many barriers in accessing medical and health care services.

2. Research methods

Based on an overview of data sources from previous studies, this study points out barriers in accessing health care services for ethnic minorities living in the land border areas of Vietnam. The authors collected documents including scientific journal articles, scientific reports, books, articles in conference proceedings, legal documents, and statistical reports of Vietnam and the world on public health and health care, etc. The main data sources were taken from <https://scholar.google.com/> and <https://www.google.com/>. The main keywords used by the author are "access to health care services for ethnic minorities, barriers to accessing health care services for ethnic minorities, access to health care services for ethnic minorities in the land border areas of Vietnam".

3. Results and discussion

In Vietnam, access to and use of health care services for ethnic minorities, especially ethnic minorities living in mountainous and border areas, is still limited. Poor people living in mountainous areas are 6 times less likely to access health care services than rich people in the plains (DN Anh & Thao, 2022). The infant mortality rate in ethnic minority areas is 4 times higher than that of Kinh and Hoa people (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2020). Ethnic minorities in border areas continue to suffer from disadvantages in accessing health care services and are unable to obtain all the health care services they need due to a range of barriers they face. Specifically:

3.1. Geographical and topographical barriers

In Vietnam, most of the land border areas are mountainous areas with rugged terrain and difficult transportation (Dong, 2021). In particular, in the northern region, the border with China has complex terrain, with nearly 80% of the area being mountainous. The Vietnam - Laos border is mainly steep mountainous areas with complex terrain, strongly divided by high mountains and deep ravines, rugged terrain, and a lack of essential transportation systems and infrastructure and poor quality (Thanh et al., 2017). In general, Vietnam's land border areas are still mostly remote mountainous areas with difficult transportation. Most of the border passes through mountain peaks or slopes and through tropical forests and rugged mountains (Thanh et al., 2017). Therefore, although the government and localities have made efforts to invest, infrastructure and transportation are still very limited. According to statistics nationwide, the percentage of villages in ethnic minority communes in border areas that still do not have

electricity is 3.7%, while the percentage of villages without electricity in ethnic minority communes in general is only 1.4%. Along with that, only 75.2% of villages in border areas have solid roads to the commune center, while the percentage of villages in ethnic minority areas that have solid roads to the commune center nationwide is nearly 90% (Vietnam Ethnic Committee & General Statistics Office, 2020).

Chart 1: Average distance from remote, border communes to medical examination and treatment facilities (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2022)

(Unit: km)

In Vietnam, the system of medical examination and treatment facilities includes 4 levels from high to low: (1) Central level; (2) Provincial and centrally-run city level; (3) District, county, town, provincial city level; (4) Commune, ward, town level and medical staff at village and hamlet level. Of which, central and provincial level medical facilities are mainly concentrated in large cities and urban areas (Tuan, 2023; Vietnam National Assembly, 2023). To access these medical facilities, ethnic minorities in border areas have to travel an average distance nearly 2 times higher than in other areas. Of which, the average distance from a remote, border commune to a regional general clinic is 17.1 km, to a district health center is 20.7 km, to a provincial hospital is 69.0 km and to all types of central hospitals is 82.0 km (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2022) (Chart 1). Currently, ethnic minorities in border areas mainly access medical facilities at the commune and district levels. However, due to the geographical and topographical characteristics of the land border areas, they are often far from the center, have inconvenient transportation, complex terrain, interspersed populations, underdeveloped infrastructure, limited socio-economic conditions, shortages and backwardness, etc., so ethnic minorities living in border areas still have fewer opportunities to access and choose health care services than people living in other areas (Vietnam Ethnic Committee & General Statistics Office, 2020). Access to provincial and central health facilities for ethnic minorities in border areas is very limited due to the long distances and difficult travel. The rugged terrain, long

geographical distances and difficult traffic conditions have been and are causing obstacles in accessing medical staff and health care facilities, thereby affecting the health care of ethnic minorities in land border areas.

3.2. Economic barriers

Cost burden is one of the next barriers that makes it difficult for ethnic minorities in border areas to access health care services (United Nations Population Fund in Vietnam & Help Age International in Viet Nam, 2021). Over the years, the Vietnamese government has made continuous efforts to effectively implement policies to directly or indirectly support ethnic minorities. Nearly half of ethnic minority households residing in border communes receive financial and material support from programs, policies, and projects of the state or non-state units, organizations, and individuals. However, such support is still very limited, so ethnic minorities in border areas on land are still facing poverty and economic difficulties (World Bank Group, 2019).

Due to the rugged terrain, large mountainous areas, and small population, the population density of ethnic minorities living in border areas is very sparse (Chien, 2024). The northern border provinces have a population of over 4 million people, with an average population density of about 76 people/km². The economic and cultural life of the people is low. Most border areas have very poor infrastructure and many difficulties in the development process. People here have low educational levels and limited understanding. The economic activities of ethnic minorities are still self-sufficient, and the conditions for economic and social development are particularly difficult (Thanh et al., 2017). The poverty of ethnic minorities in border areas has limited their access to resources and they receive fewer health care services. According to the research results of authors Dang Nguyen Anh and Nguyen Thi Phuong Thao, in Vietnam, rich people have 4 times more access to health care services than poor people. Poor people go to the hospital less and spend less on health care than rich people (DN Anh & Thao, 2022). Meanwhile, the poverty and near-poverty rate of ethnic minority households is still 35.5%, 3.5 times higher than the national poverty and near-poverty rate. The rate of poor and near-poor ethnic minority households in border areas is up to 48.4%, 1.5 times higher than other areas (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2023). The cost is too high, not suitable for the economic context of local people, leading to people rarely using health services (United Nations Population Fund in Vietnam & Vietnam Ministry of Health, 2017). In 2022, the average expenditure per person for inpatient medical examination and treatment was approximately 9.0 million VND (about 360 USD) and per person for outpatient medical examination and treatment was nearly 1.4 million VND (about 56 USD) (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2023). High costs prevent ethnic minorities from seeking medical care because they do not have

enough money (PT Anh & Viet, 2020). Only over 20% of the poor and near - poor have access to provincial and central hospitals (Vietnam The General Statistics Office, 2013). Research by UNFPA and the Ministry of Health also shows that due to difficulty in accessing health workers, health care facilities and the inability to pay for services at health facilities, ethnic minority women, including ethnic minority women in border areas, want to give birth at home and limit access to prenatal care services (United Nations Population Fund in Vietnam & Vietnam Ministry of Health, 2017). In general, ethnic minority communes in border areas have very difficult economic conditions, which is also one of the barriers affecting the health care of ethnic minorities living in land border areas.

3.3. Barriers to facilities and human resources at the grassroots level

Due to the rugged mountainous terrain and inconvenient transportation, large hospitals are often not built in border areas (Laksono & Wulandari, 2021). This makes people in border areas have to travel very long distances to access the hospital system (Glinos & Wismar, 2013). Therefore, ethnic minorities in border areas often go to commune - level health stations for medical examination and treatment. However, the conditions of facilities and quality of medical staff at commune - level health stations in ethnic minority communes in border areas are currently limited. Most ethnic minority communes have health stations, but the facilities are not yet guaranteed. Nearly 50% of health stations still do not have adequate facilities. The number of grassroots medical staff is still lacking and their professional skills and expertise are weak. The rate of communes with national standard health stations in border areas in general is 78.5%. Nearly 60% of health stations are still concentrated in extremely disadvantaged communes and in land border areas that have not yet met standards (Vietnam Ethnic Committee & General Statistics Office, 2020).

At commune - level health stations in ethnic minority areas, only 14.3% of leaders and medical staff have medical qualifications and only 13.4% of leaders and medical staff at Commune health stations in ethnic minority border areas have doctors. Over 80% of the leaders and staff at commune health stations are doctors, nurses or caregivers. Although Vietnam has implemented many programs, projects and policies to attract doctors to work at commune health stations in ethnic minority areas, currently only 77.2% of commune health stations in ethnic minority areas nationwide have doctors, while the percentage of health stations in ethnic minority border areas with doctors is only 70.0% (Table 1).

Table 1: Proportion of leaders and medical staff at commune health stations in ethnic minority areas by level (Vietnam Ethnic Committee & General Statistics Office, 2020)

Area	Ratio of leaders and medical staff divided by level (%)						Percentage of health stations with doctors (%)
	Doctor	Doctor/ Nurse/ Caregiver	Midwife	Pharmacist	Pharmacist	Other staff	
Nationwide	14.3	54.8	15.1	9.5	1.0	5.3	77.2
Border area	13.4	55.0	16.0	8.4	0.8	6.4	70.0

In border areas, due to difficult transportation and limited opportunities for people to access medical services, health care and protection, the village health network in the communes has received attention for development. Therefore, the rate of village health in border areas is up to 93.7%, higher than other areas at 82.7%. However, the village health staff is very lacking in quantity and weak in expertise. The village health staff is not highly qualified, has not received attention for development in terms of qualifications and skills, and the working regime is mainly part-time. The rate of trained village health workers is only about 70 - 80% (CVB Thu, 2024).

In addition, the allowances that village health workers receive are very low, and there are no good incentives and incentive mechanisms to attract high-quality human resources. Currently, village health workers during their working period will receive a monthly allowance of 0.5 and 0.3 times the basic salary (Vietnam Prime Minister, 2009). With the current basic salary of 2.34 million VND/month (about 93.6 USD), the allowance for this group will range from 702,000 VND/month (about 28.8 USD) to 1,170,000 VND/month (about 46.8 USD) (Vietnam Government, 2024). Village health workers have to take on a lot of work while the allowance is still low, which will make it difficult to create enthusiasm for work and not attract highly qualified staff, thus reducing the effectiveness of health care for ethnic minorities in Vietnam's land border areas.

3.4. Language and cultural barriers

Research from the United States and the United Kingdom indicates that people from ethnic minority communities have more problems accessing and interacting with services than the general population (Mental Health Commission, 2016). Cultural differences, language, and limited awareness have created barriers to health care for the majority of patients from ethnic minority communities (Ala, 2005; Chauhan et al., 2023; Johnson, 1996; Kapadia et al., 2022). In Vietnam, language and cultural barriers are also directly affecting the ability of ethnic minorities living in border areas to access health services (Mbuya, Atwood, & Nam, 2019). Poor literacy, language difficulties, and lack of priority policies have had negative impacts on

the accessibility and utilization of health care services among ethnic minorities in border areas (Hayanga et al., 2021).

Limited awareness along with traditional customs and beliefs of ethnic minorities also have a negative impact on the general health care of the people, especially maternal and child health care. Many ethnic minorities still do not use health services, they do not go to health centers to give birth but still give birth at home (Nga, Duong, Kien, & Minh, 2020). Many ethnic minority women believe that giving birth is a natural human process. They want to give birth at home rather than at medical facilities, unless complications occur. They want to be as close to their family and home as possible during labor and delivery (United Nations Population Fund in Vietnam & Vietnam Ministry of Health, 2017).

In Vietnam, ethnic minorities in border areas often use lower levels of health services than the Kinh people. One of the reasons for this situation is limited awareness and difficult living conditions. The Vietnamese government has policies on free health insurance for ethnic minorities living in areas with difficult socio-economic conditions (National Assembly, 2008; Vietnam Government, 2023). However, there are still ethnic minority people who do not know how to use the benefits of health insurance. They are still concerned about the cost of medical examination and treatment, so they do not use services at medical facilities. In addition, ethnic minorities often treat their own illnesses, they do not recognize the dangerous signs of illness, they also rarely receive expensive services and often do not use the same services as Kinh patients, even though the ethnic minority patients have the same illness, are the same age and are the same gender as Kinh patients (DN Anh & Thao, 2022). The fact that ethnic minorities in border areas have little access to high-quality health services can also lead to difficulties in mobilizing social resources as well as state policy commitments to improve the limitations of the current health system (United Nations Population Fund in Vietnam & Vietnam Ministry of Health, 2017).

3.5. Policy barriers

In Vietnam, the implementation of public health care policies for ethnic minorities in border areas has achieved certain results but still faces many difficulties and limitations. Currently, the Government has not yet had any health care programs specifically for ethnic minorities in border areas. Health care policies and ethnic minority policies are still placed together and integrated with poverty reduction policies. Moreover, many policies have been issued by the Government, but in the implementation process, there are still many difficulties due to lack of funds to build facilities and purchase medical equipment at the grassroots level. Along with that, support and incentive policies to attract qualified medical staff to work in ethnic minority border areas are still limited. Although the state has preferential policies for

human resources working in localities in region 135, these policies are not attractive enough for high-quality human resources (CVB Thu, 2024).

4. Conclusion and recommendations

After nearly 40 years of renovation, Vietnam has achieved many achievements in various fields, including remarkable and remarkable achievements in the field of health and health care for the people. However, ethnic minorities, especially ethnic minorities in mountainous areas, are still facing many limitations in health care. The overall results show that due to the terrain characteristics of Vietnam's land border areas, which are mainly mountainous and highland areas, people's lives still face many difficulties. Therefore, ethnic minorities here also face a series of barriers in health care. "Health and a good life" is one of the sustainable development goals that Vietnam is aiming for. To achieve this goal, in the current context, Vietnam needs to continue to implement measures to help remove barriers and increase access to health care services for ethnic minorities living in land border areas, including:

- Completing infrastructure, improving the quality of roads and developing the economy of ethnic minorities in border areas are prerequisites to help improve the quality of life and increase access to health care services for ethnic minorities in border areas.

- The Vietnamese government needs to continue to improve the policy system to create changes at the management level, ensuring that health programs have strong support from the government and relevant parties. On that basis, local authorities with land borders need to implement policies suitable to local characteristics and meet the needs of ethnic minorities in accessing health care services in the area.

- To increase access to health care services for ethnic minorities in border areas, the Vietnamese government needs to promote activities to improve the capacity of the primary health care system at the commune level. Health services at commune health centers are the most suitable places to provide health care services for ethnic minorities in border areas. Therefore, commune health facilities in ethnic minority border areas need to be invested in upgrading their infrastructure and medical equipment to be able to provide on - site health care services for the people. Along with that, local authorities and the health sector need to have preferential policies to attract qualified medical human resources and strengthen training to improve the capacity of local human resources.

- Local authorities and the health sector need to have strategies to encourage the participation of ethnic minority communities in border areas in using health services. The health sector needs to have communication campaigns with ethnic minority communities in border areas to change people's awareness, helping people see the benefits of using health care services.

Local authorities need to cooperate with the health sector to have guidelines on the use of insurance and easier access to health insurance.

Ethical Statement

No animals were used in this study; thus, no ethical approval is required.

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Declaration of Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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